

Reaction of IET3626 (TNAU13613) to *Helminthosporium* in Tamil Nadu, India

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Helminthosporium is a major rice disease in Tamil Nadu, primarily in the second crop season (Oct.—Feb.). All existing varieties are affected. To identify a good donor parent for resistance to *Helminthosporium*, many hybrid derivatives have been screened at Aduthurai for several years. Among the cultures tested, only IET3626 (TNAU13613 – a mutant of TKM6) was rated as resistant to moderately resistant. It exhibited a similar reaction at other AICRIP centers (see table). □

Reaction of IET3626 (TNAU13613) *Helminthosporium* in tests at various centers in India AICRIP, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Center	Reaction ^a	
	1976	1977
Coochbehar	—	MR
Cuttack	MR	R
Faizabad	MR	MR
Ponnampet	—	MR
Coimbatore	R	—
Kalimpong I	MR	—
Kalimpong II	MR	—
Aduthurai	MR	R

^a MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant.

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Need for varieties resistant to the whitebacked planthopper in the Punjab

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The whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* was not an important rice pest when farmers grew traditional tall varieties in the Punjab. But with the cultivation of semidwarf varieties, WBPH began to cause alarming damage. Rice was hopperburned by WBPH in the rice seasons of 1967, 1972, 1975, and 1978 (see photo). In 1978 WBPH severely damaged a number of promising breeding lines in replicated yield trials at the Rice

Research Station, Kapurthala (see table).

All the varieties in the table were considered susceptible, but the degree of damage varied. WBPH began to damage rice in mid-August. First damaged were the more leafy varieties PR274, PR437, PR558, PR559, and PR562. The insects started to migrate to other varieties at the milk stage. At the end of September, 10% BHC dust was applied at 25 kg/ha to salvage seed. Thus, the varieties with little damage were those not exposed to the WBPH attack for sufficient time at the proper growth stage.

The susceptibility of varieties with low damage was confirmed by their reaction in different replications. For example,

Whitebacked planthopper damage to some promising rice breeding lines in 1978. Approximate pooled damage in 3 replications estimated by visual observations. Punjab, India.

Cultivar	Cross	Damage (%)
PR106	IR8//Peta 5/Belle Patna	35
PR445	Basmati 370/Hamsa	35
PR560	IR8/Basmati 370	35
PR561	Basmati 370/Hamsa	35
PR563	Basmati 370/Jaya	35
PR270	Basmati 370/Hamsa	50
PR440	Basmati 370/Hamsa	50
PR484	Mutant Basmati 370 (0.4% EMS)	50
PR564	PP72/Mutant 65	50
PR565	IR8/Basmati 370	50
IET5862	Improved Sabarmati/Sona	50
IET6250	Improved Sabarmati/Sona	50
IET6251	Improved Sabarmati/Sona	50
R 36-2486	—	50
PR151	Mutant Basmati 370 (40 Kr)	70
PR274	Basmati 370/Hamsa	70
PR437	Basmati 370/IR8	70
PR476	Mutant Basmati 370 (0.4% EMS)	70
PR503	Basmati 370/Hamsa	70
CRM 10-57-10-4	Irradiated Basmati 370	70
CRM 5667-1	Irradiated Basmati 370	70
CRM 5713-8	Irradiated Basmati 370	70
CRM 5713-13	Irradiated Basmati 370	70
IET 3618	Sabarmati/Ratna	70
IET 4110	Basmati 370/IR8-36	70
IET 5729	Mutant Basmati 370	70
IET 5861	Improved Sabarmati/Sona	70
SFC I	—	70
SFC III	—	70
Basmati 370	—	70
PR558	Basmati 370/Hamsa	95
PR559	Basmati 370/Hamsa	95
PR562	Basmati 370/Hamsa	95

PR106 had less than 20% damage in one replication but more than 60% of its plot was completely destroyed in another replication. The same was true for PR445, PR560, PR561, and PR563.

A survey conducted by the Indian Directorate of Quarantine, Plant Protection, and Storage also revealed hopperburn on IR8 on farmers' fields in the Punjab in 1978. An objective of our future rice breeding programs is to develop WBPH-resistant varieties. □

Evaluation of rice strains for resistance to gall midge and leaf roller

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Rice entries received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for resistance to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* and leaf roller

Hopperburn in PR558 rice, caused by WBPH in 1978 at the Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, India.

Cnaphalocrosis medinalis in a field trial laid out in a randomized block design at Madurai Agricultural College Farm in

1977-78. Of the 265 entries evaluated, 20 had minimum incidence of gall midge and leaf roller (see table). IET 6181, 6286, 6293, and 6195, on which the incidence of both gall midge and leaf roller was much lower than that on the susceptible varieties, appear to have some resistance to both insects. □

Rice entries resistant to gall midge and leaf roller, mean of two replications in 3 periods, Madurai, India.

IET no.	Designation	Parents	Tillers (%) affected by gall midge	Leaves (%) affected by leaf roller
<i>Resistant to both gall midge and leaf roller</i>				
6181	WGL20691	CR44/W12708	0.9	7.1
6286	CR 95-181-2	Leaung 152/IR8	0	9.3
6293	WGL 26445	—	0	8.8
6295	RNR 32341	—	0.4	7.9
<i>Resistant to gall midge</i>				
4600	RP 872-1-2	Cauvery/W12787	0	—
5700	IR2071-636-5-5	IR24/CR94-13	0.8	—
5703	HYN 17-5-4	Hoyoku/Zinya	0.5	—
5981	OR 100-7	Kumar/Bala	0.9	—
5116	RP894-5-1-5-4	CR44-35/W12708	0.5	—
5233	RP872-20-4-3-4	Cauvery/W12787	0.4	—
5711	RP974-173-4	Sona/RP9-4	0	—
6257	1140-47-2-46-19	—	0.3	—
2911	RPW 6-17	IR8/Siam 29	0.7	—
3347	ORS 46 1	Leaung 152//IR8*2	0	—
3354	RP350-57-1-1	820862/820916	0.2	—
3356	RP352-28-1-1-4	IR8/PTB18//Eswarakora/IR8	0	—
3362	RP9-10-3-2-1-1	IR8/W1251	0.7	—
6287	CR 95-26-1	Leaung 152/IR8	0.7	—
6292	WGL 26442	—	0.3	—
—	RPW 6-13	—	0.7	—
<i>Susceptible check</i>				
Jaya			17.2	60.1
Pankaj			12.0	—

Outbreak of rice thrips in Kuttanadu, Kerala, India

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The usual farming practice in Kuttanadu is to grow a single rice crop (locally called *punja*) from October to February. Farmers have recently attempted to grow a second rice crop from April to September, which is almost free of serious insect problems.

The rice thrip *Buliothrips biformis* has only recently become a serious punja-season pest, especially on the late crop. The transplanted crop suffered a serious thrip outbreak in May and June 1978. The main symptoms were leaf rolling and drying at the leaf tips. In severe infestations the plants were stunted and the lower leaves killed.

Observations of 15 varieties and lines